

A design of a smart farm system for cattle monitoring

Khalid El Moutaouakil, Nouredine Falih

LIMATI Laboratory, Department of Computer Science, Polydisciplinary Faculty, University of Sultan Moulay Slimane,
Beni Mellal, Morocco

Article Info

Article history:

Received May 30, 2023

Revised Jul 7, 2023

Accepted Jul 16, 2023

Keywords:

Internet of things

Machine learning

Precision livestock farming

Smart cattle monitoring

Smart farm system

ABSTRACT

The integration of technology in agriculture has led to the adoption of smart farming systems, which are becoming increasingly popular for optimizing resources, reducing labor costs, and improving efficiency. This article presents a design of a smart cattle monitoring farm system, which focuses on monitoring individual animal behavior and health, improving resource management, and optimizing overall farm efficiency. The proposed system integrates various internet of things (IoT) sensors, communication technologies, and cloud computing to provide a real-time monitoring solution for cattle farms. The system uses machine learning (ML) algorithms to analyze data on cattle behavior, health, and performance, which can be accessed through web and mobile applications by farmers to proactively monitor their herd. The adoption of the system promises good results for intelligently transforming traditional cattle farming by reducing manual monitoring time and achieving a good accuracy in early detection of diseases, automated tracking of estrus cycles, and location mapping of cattle across the farm fields.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](#) license.

Corresponding Author:

Khalid El Moutaouakil

LIMATI Laboratory, Department of Computer Science, Polydisciplinary Faculty

University of Sultan Moulay Slimane

Mghila, BP 592, Beni Mellal, Morocco

Email: elmoutaouakil.kh@gmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

The global demand for food products is on the rise, putting significant pressure on farmers to increase their production efficiency, particularly livestock [1]. Additionally, climate change and the scarcity of natural resources necessitate the development of more sustainable and efficient farming practices [2]. Precision livestock farming (PLF) has emerged as a solution to these challenges, incorporating technology to optimize the management of individual animals and enable data-driven decision-making [3].

Agriculture is an essential sector that contributes significantly to the economy of every nation [4]. In recent times, there has been a growing interest in smart farming systems, which use advanced technologies to enhance agricultural productivity, reduce resource usage, and promote sustainable farming practices [5]. Cattle monitoring is a vital aspect of livestock farming, and it is crucial for livestock farmers to keep track of the health, behavior, and location of their animals [6].

Traditional cattle farming practices face numerous challenges, including increasing demand for food production, limited resources, and growing concerns about animal welfare and environmental impact [7]. To address these issues, there has been a surge of interest in the development and implementation of smart agriculture technologies [8]. One promising area is the development of smart monitoring systems for cattle farms [9].

Raising livestock like cattle requires close monitoring and management to optimize health, growth, and productivity [10]. Traditional cattle monitoring on farms is a labor-intensive process where farmers must manually check on each individual cow regularly [11]. The emergence of internet of things (IoT) technologies,

such as sensors, connectivity, cloud platforms, and artificial intelligence (AI) techniques like machine learning (ML), enables smart cattle monitoring with much less human intervention [12].

In recent years, the integration of technology in agriculture has been rapidly growing [13]. Smart farming systems are becoming increasingly popular. Especially for their ability to optimize resources, reduce labor costs, and improve overall efficiency [14].

A smart cattle monitoring farm system aims to improve farm productivity, animal welfare, and resource management by using advanced technologies to collect and analyze data in real-time [15]. These systems typically rely on a combination of IoT devices, ML algorithms, and cloud-based services to monitor cattle health, behavior, and environmental conditions [16]. The smart cattle monitoring farm system aims to transform traditional cattle farming by data-driven decision-making, and automation of various processes [17].

This paper proposes a complete smart cattle monitoring system using IoT and AI techniques. The system consists of cattle mounted IoT sensors like GPS tags, temperature sensors, accelerometer trackers that continuously send data to a cloud platform. The raw sensor data is then processed and analyzed using ML algorithms to gain insights into cattle health, behavior, and location. Farmers can access visualized reports and real-time alerts through web and mobile applications to proactively monitor their herd. The system focuses on monitoring the health and behavior of individual cattle, improving resource management, and increasing overall farm efficiency. The paper will discuss the main components of the system, including monitoring devices, data collection and processing, communication protocols, and decision-making techniques.

2. METHOD

The smart cattle monitoring farm system can be divided into five main layers: sensing, data acquisition and processing, data analysis and decision-making, visualization and communication layers. These layers are depicted in Figure 1. The following sections describe these layers in detail.

Figure 1. A general overview of the system layer

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we provide a detailed description of all the components comprising the proposed system. The discussion is organized into several sub-sections for clarity and comprehensiveness. Each sub-section delves into specific aspects of the system, offering comprehensive insights into its functions.

3.1. Sensing layer

The sensing layer consists of various monitoring devices that collect data on individual cattle and the farm environment [18]. Data collection is achieved using a variety of IoT devices strategically placed throughout the farm. These devices include sensors for monitoring environmental conditions (e.g., temperature, humidity, air quality pressure), wearable devices for monitoring cattle health and behavior (e.g., GPS trackers, accelerometers, heart rate monitors), and cameras for visual monitoring of cattle and farm infrastructure Figure 2. These devices can be divided into two categories: wearable and non-wearable sensors.

Figure 2. Sensing layer

3.1.1. Wearable sensors

Wearable sensors are attached to the animals and provide real-time data on their physiological and behavioral parameters. The wearable sensors are included in Table 1. It outlines their functionalities and use cases.

Table 1. Wearable sensors

Sensors	Functionalities
GPS trackers	These devices are attached to the animal's collar or ear tag and provide location data, allowing farmers to track animal movements and grazing patterns.
Accelerometers	These sensors measure the animal's movement in three axes and can be used to detect various behaviors such as walking, standing, lying, eating, and rumination.
Temperature and humidity	These sensors help monitor the environment within barns or outdoors, enabling farmers to maintain optimal conditions for cattle welfare and productivity.
Pressure	These sensors play an important role in smart cattle monitoring systems by providing a means of measuring and monitoring the weight and movement of individual animals within a herd. They can be used to track the feeding and drinking habits of cattle, monitor their overall health and welfare, and identify potential issues before they become serious.
Heart rate	These sensors measure the animal's heart rate, providing information on their fitness and stress levels. This information can be used to identify potential health issues, which may require veterinary attention.
RFID tags	By attaching RFID tags to the cattle herd, farmers can uniquely identify each animal, track their movements, and collect data on various parameters, such as milk production, weight gain, and health status.

3.1.2. Non-wearable sensors

Data on environmental parameters and animal behavior is collected by non-wearable sensors installed in the farm environment. These sensors offer insights into the conditions of the farm and the behavior of the animals. A selection of commonly used non-wearable sensors can be found in Table 2.

Table 2. Non-wearable sensors

Sensors	Functionalities
Video and image	Cameras can be used to monitor cattle behavior, welfare, and productivity visually. Computer vision techniques can be applied to analyze images and videos, enabling automated detection of events such as calving, mating, or signs of illness.
Microphones	These sensors capture audio data and can be used to detect vocalizations associated with stress or illness.
Weight scales	These devices measure the animal's weight, allowing farmers to track growth and detect potential health issues.
Feed and water intake	These sensors monitor the consumption of feed and water, providing information on the animal's nutritional status.
Electronic gates	These gates provide means of controlling the movement of cattle and collecting data on their behavior. These gates can be equipped with sensors that detect when a cow passes through, allowing for individual identification and tracking of each animal's movements.
Infrared thermography	These cameras plays an important role in smart cattle monitoring systems by providing an effective way to monitor the health and well-being of individual animals in a herd. This technology uses infrared cameras to detect and measure the heat emitted by the bodies of cattle, which can be an indicator of various health conditions.
Air quality	These sensors play an important role in smart cattle monitoring systems by providing a means of monitoring and controlling the environment within the barn or other housing facilities where cattle are kept. These sensors can detect and measure the levels of various pollutants, gases, and other environmental factors that can affect the health and comfort of the animals.

3.2. Data acquisition and processing layer

The data acquired by sensors needs to be processed and analyzed to extract useful insights. Data acquisition and processing components of the smart farm system are designed to efficiently gather, store, and preprocess data from the sensors in real-time. The data from the sensors would be collected and processed using a edge computing devices, which would preprocess the data and send it to the cloud or local server for further analysis Figure 3. Further details on the data acquisition and processing components are provided in the subsections below.

Figure 3. Data acquisition and processing layer

3.2.1. Data acquisition system

Once the sensors collect data, the next step is to acquire it. A data acquisition system is responsible for receiving data from sensors and aggregating it into a usable format. For that, we are using edge computing devices. Edge computing devices are typically small, low-power devices that are placed near the sensors and other data sources, allowing them to collect data in real-time without the need for centralized processing or storage. This enables faster and more efficient data acquisition, as well as improved data security and privacy [19].

3.2.2. Data processing system

After acquiring data, it needs to be processed to extract meaningful insights. Data processing involves cleaning, filtering, and analyzing data. Later, ML algorithms can be used to detect anomalies, predict patterns, and identify potential health issues in cattle.

The data processing layer is responsible for storing, processing, and analyzing the data collected by the sensing layer. This layer typically consists of a combination of edge computing devices (e.g., gateways, microcontrollers) and cloud-based servers. The data processing layer performs several functions included in Table 3.

Table 3. Data processing layer components

Units	Functions
Data storage	The collected data is stored in databases or cloud storage platforms for long-term archiving and future analysis. The data storage component is responsible for storing the pre-processed data and the results of the ML algorithms. This component is implemented using cloud-based services to ensure scalability, reliability, and security. The data storage component also provides APIs for accessing the stored data, enabling integration with other farm management systems and visualization tools.
Data preprocessing	Raw data is cleaned, normalized, and transformed to a suitable format for analysis. The data processing component is responsible for pre-processing the raw data collected from IoT devices and transforming it into a structured format suitable for storage and analysis. This includes tasks such as data cleaning, normalization, and feature extraction. Smart cattle monitoring systems generate vast amounts of data that need to be stored and processed efficiently. Data processing can be performed using big data platforms like Hadoop and Spark, which support the analysis of large datasets in parallel and real-time.
Cloud computing	The data collected from the sensors can be analyzed and processed in real-time, with insights presented on a dashboard or mobile app for farm managers. The data should be stored in a cloud-based system, which allows for easy access. The data would be stored in a cloud-based storage solution such as Amazon Web Services (AWS), Google Cloud Platform (GCP), or Microsoft Azure, where it can be analyzed and processed. The cloud computing infrastructure provides storage and computing resources for the collected data. The cloud computing platform can be used to analyze the data collected by the sensors to identify patterns and trends in the behavior and health of the cattle. ML algorithms can be used to analyze the data and provide insights into the health and behavior of the cattle.

3.3. Data analysis and decision-making layer

The data analysis and decision support component is responsible for providing actionable insights and recommendations to farmers based on the collected data and the results of ML and deep learning algorithms. This includes tools for visualizing and exploring the data. As well as advanced analytics capabilities, such as predictive modeling and optimization algorithms Figure 4.

Figure 4. Data analysis and decision-making layer

The decision support component also includes a user-friendly interface for managing the system, configuring IoT devices, and accessing the collected data. The decision-making layer involves the analysis of collected data using AI and ML algorithms. This layer can be further divided into several units included in Table 4.

Table 4. Decision-making layer components

Units	Functions
Feature Extraction	Relevant features are extracted from the preprocessed data using various ML techniques.
Data Analysis	AI and ML algorithms are used to analyze the data and generate insights about cattle health, behavior, and farm management.
Anomaly detection	The system can detect deviations from normal patterns, which may indicate health issues or other problems.

The decision-making layer uses insights gained from data analysis to make informed decisions about farm management and cattle care [20]. Examples of decisions that can be made using smart cattle monitoring systems include: identifying sick or injured cattle and providing appropriate medical care, adjusting feeding schedules and rations based on individual cattle needs, detecting signs of heat stress and taking preventive measures and optimizing grazing patterns and pasture management. These examples highlight the diverse applications of smart cattle monitoring systems in enhancing farm operations and animal welfare.

The decision-making processing component applies ML algorithms to the pre-processed data to identify patterns and detect anomalies. For example, algorithms for activity recognition can be used to classify cattle behavior (e.g., grazing, resting, walking). While algorithms for anomaly detection can be used to identify potential health issues or environmental problems.

3.4. Visualization layer

A user interface that displays the collected data, insights, and alerts to farmers is designed with an intuitive and user-friendly interface to help quick decision-making. A user-friendly dashboard or mobile app would be developed to display the collected data, insights, and alerts to farmers. The interface would allow farmers to view the current status of their herd and make informed decisions Figure 5.

Figure 5. Visualization layer

A user-friendly dashboard is essential to display insights to farmers. The dashboard should display information in a clear and concise manner, highlighting any issues that need attention, such as cattle health problems, feed consumption, and other parameters that may impact production. By providing a comprehensive overview, the dashboard enables farmers to make decisions and take prompt action for improved farm management.

Real-time information on the health, behavior, and location of cattle can be conveniently accessed by farmers through mobile applications. These applications can be accessed from smartphones or tablets, offering farmers the flexibility to stay updated on their cattle's well-being. Additionally, the mobile applications can provide alerts and notifications whenever anomalies are detected in the data collected by the sensors, ensuring prompt attention to any issues that may arise.

The smart farm system should have automation capabilities to automate tasks such as feeding, watering, or cleaning the barn. This can help reduce labor costs and improve efficiency. For example, sensors could detect when a feeding trough is empty and trigger an automated feeding system.

Based on the decisions made, control systems are employed to automate various processes and tasks on the farm. Examples of such automation include: automated feeding systems that adjust rations and schedules based on individual cattle needs, climate control systems that maintain optimal temperature and humidity levels in the barn, robotic milking systems that optimize milking frequency and reduce labor costs. These examples illustrate how control systems contribute to streamlining operations and improving productivity on the farm.

The control system is responsible for controlling various aspects of the farm, such as lighting, temperature, and feeding. This system is integrated with the monitoring system to provide automated control based on data insights. This integration ensures that farm operations are optimized and responsive to real-time conditions, enhancing efficiency and effectiveness.

The system to send alerts and notifications to farm managers if unusual activity is detected. This can help farmers to take action to prevent or mitigate potential issues. For example, if a cow is not moving or showing signs of illness, the system would send an alert to the farmer. An important feature of a cattle monitoring system is the ability to alert farmers about any critical issues. Alerts can be sent via email, SMS, or push notifications to mobile devices.

3.5. Communication layer

For effective functioning, a reliable communication infrastructure is vital to facilitate the transmission of sensor data to the central processing unit and enable remote access to the system Figure 6. This infrastructure ensures seamless connectivity. It enables the timely transfer of data and the remote monitoring and control capabilities. Various wired and wireless communication protocols can be used in the smart cattle monitoring system. Table 5 describes the features of the main ones. It describes the characteristics and features of each protocol.

Figure 6. Communication layer

Table 5. Communication protocols

Protocol	Features
ZigBee	A low-power, low-cost wireless communication standard suitable for short-range data transmission [21].
LoRaWAN	Long range wide area network (LoRaWAN) has a long-range, low-power wireless communication protocol that can cover large distances in rural areas [22].
Wi-Fi	A widely available and high-speed wireless communication standard, suitable for transmitting large amounts of data [23].
Ethernet	A wired communication protocol that provides high-speed and reliable data transmission [24].
WSN	Wireless sensor networks (WSNs) consist of multiple sensors that communicate with each other wirelessly. They can be used to cover a large area and collect data in real-time [25].
Cellular Networks	These networks use cellular technology to transmit data from the sensors to the central server. They can be used in areas with cellular coverage [26].

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, setting up a cattle monitoring smart farm system requires careful consideration of the components involved and how they interact with each other. With the right architecture, farmers can gain valuable insights into their cattle's health and wellbeing, helping to improve production and reduce costs. This paper presented the design of a smart cattle monitoring farm system that aims to improve farm productivity, animal welfare, and resource management. The proposed system uses a combination of IoT devices, ML algorithms, and cloud-based services to collect and analyze data in real-time. By incorporating these key elements into a cattle monitoring smart farm system, farmers can benefit from better decision-making, improved herd health, and increased productivity.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Fróna, J. Szenderák, and M. Harangi-Rákos, "The challenge of feeding the world," *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, vol. 11, no. 20, p. 5816, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.3390/su11205816.
- [2] M. M. Maja and S. F. Ayano, "The impact of population growth on natural resources and farmers' capacity to adapt to climate change in low-income countries," *Earth Systems and Environment*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 271–283, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.1007/s41748-021-00209-6.
- [3] P. Niloofar *et al.*, "Data-driven decision support in livestock farming for improved animal health, welfare and greenhouse gas emissions: Overview and challenges," *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, vol. 190, p. 106406, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.compag.2021.106406.
- [4] E. Loizou, C. Karelakis, K. Galanopoulos, and K. Mattas, "The role of agriculture as a development tool for a regional economy," *Agricultural Systems*, vol. 173, pp. 482–490, Jul. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.agry.2019.04.002.
- [5] M. J. Adegbeye *et al.*, "Sustainable agriculture options for production, greenhouse gasses and pollution alleviation, and nutrient recycling in emerging and transitional nations - An overview," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 242, p. 118319, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.118319.
- [6] A. Gehlot, P. K. Malik, R. Singh, S. V. Akram, and T. Alsuwian, "Dairy 4.0: Intelligent communication ecosystem for the cattle animal welfare with blockchain and IoT enabled technologies," *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)*, vol. 12, no. 14, p. 7316, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.3390/app12147316.
- [7] S. Neethirajan and B. Kemp, "Digital livestock farming," *Sensing and Bio-Sensing Research*, vol. 32, p. 100408, Jun. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.sbsr.2021.100408.
- [8] M. S. Farooq, S. Riaz, A. Abid, K. Abid, and M. A. Naem, "A survey on the role of IoT in agriculture for the implementation of smart farming," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 156237–156271, 2019, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2949703.
- [9] K. El Moutaouakil, H. Jdi, B. Jabir, and N. Falih, "Digital Farming: A Survey on IoT-based Cattle Monitoring Systems and Dashboards," *AGRIS on-line Papers in Economics and Informatics*, vol. 15, no. 2, 2023, doi: 10.7160/aol.2023.150203.
- [10] A. Monteiro, S. Santos, and P. Gonçalves, "Precision agriculture for crop and livestock farming—Brief review," *Animals*, vol. 11, no. 8, p. 2345, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.3390/ani11082345.
- [11] K. Džermeikaitė, D. Bačėninaitė, and R. Antanaitis, "Innovations in cattle farming: Application of innovative technologies and sensors in the diagnosis of diseases," *Animals*, vol. 13, no. 5, p. 780, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.3390/ani13050780.
- [12] A. Rehman, T. Saba, M. Kashif, S. M. Fati, S. A. Bahaj, and H. Chaudhry, "A revisit of internet of things technologies for monitoring and control strategies in smart agriculture," *Agronomy*, vol. 12, no. 1, p. 127, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.3390/agronomy12010127.
- [13] H. Tian, T. Wang, Y. Liu, X. Qiao, and Y. Li, "Computer vision technology in agricultural automation —A review," *Information Processing in Agriculture*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–19, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.inpa.2019.09.006.

- [14] I. Charania and X. Li, "Smart farming: Agriculture's shift from a labor intensive to technology native industry," *Internet of Things (Netherlands)*, vol. 9, p. 100142, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.iot.2019.100142.
- [15] R. S. Upendra, I. M. Umesh, R. B. R. Varma, and B. Basavaprasad, "Technology in Indian agriculture – A review," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (IJECS)*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 1070–1077, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v20.i2.pp1070-1077.
- [16] G. Idoje, T. Dagiuklas, and M. Iqbal, "Survey for smart farming technologies: Challenges and issues," *Computers and Electrical Engineering*, vol. 92, p. 107104, Jun. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.compeleceng.2021.107104.
- [17] M. Taneja, N. Jalodia, J. Byabazaire, A. Davy, and C. Olariu, "SmartHerd management: A microservices-based fog computing–assisted IoT platform towards data-driven smart dairy farming," *Software - Practice and Experience*, vol. 49, no. 7, pp. 1055–1078, May 2019, doi: 10.1002/spe.2704.
- [18] S. L. Ullo and G. R. Sinha, "Advances in IoT and smart sensors for remote sensing and agriculture applications," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 13, no. 13, p. 2585, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.3390/rs13132585.
- [19] Y. Velayutham, N. A. A. Bakar, N. H. Hassan, and G. N. Samy, "IoT security for smart grid environment: Issues and solutions," *Jordanian Journal of Computers and Information Technology*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 13–24, 2021, doi: 10.5455/jjcit.71-1595835783.
- [20] K. El Moutaouakil, H. Jdi, B. Jabir, and N. Falih, "An IoT ecosystem-based architecture of a smart livestock farm," in *Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, vol. 656, pp. 283–293, 2023, doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-29313-9_25.
- [21] R. Mubashar, M. A. B. Siddique, A. U. Rehman, A. Asad, and A. Rasool, "Comparative performance analysis of short-range wireless protocols for wireless personal area network," *Iran Journal of Computer Science*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 201–210, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1007/s42044-021-00087-1.
- [22] N. Islam, B. Ray, and F. Pasandideh, "IoT based smart farming: Are the LPWAN technologies suitable for remote communication?," in *Proceedings - 2020 IEEE International Conference on Smart Internet of Things, SmartIoT 2020*, Aug. 2020, pp. 270–276, doi: 10.1109/SmartIoT49966.2020.00048.
- [23] C. Deng *et al.*, "IEEE 802.11be Wi-Fi 7: New challenges and opportunities," *IEEE Communications Surveys and Tutorials*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 2136–2166, 2020, doi: 10.1109/COMST.2020.3012715.
- [24] F. E. Abrahamsen, Y. Ai, and M. Cheffena, "Communication technologies for smart grid: A comprehensive survey," *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 23, p. 8087, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.3390/s21238087.
- [25] R. Ouni and K. Saleem, "Framework for sustainable wireless sensor network based environmental monitoring," *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, vol. 14, no. 14, p. 8356, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.3390/su14148356.
- [26] K. Gulati, R. S. K. Boddu, D. Kapila, S. L. Bangare, N. Chandnani, and G. Saravanan, "A review paper on wireless sensor network techniques in internet of things (IoT)," *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 51, pp. 161–165, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2021.05.067.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Khalid El Moutaouakil in 2017, he earned his Master's degree in computer engineering and systems from the Polydisciplinary Faculty of Sultan Moulay Slimane University in Beni Mellal, Morocco. Currently, he is pursuing his Ph.D. studies in the same faculty and works as a computer science teacher in a high school in Marrakech, Morocco. His research interests lie in digital agriculture, deep learning, and information systems. To reach him, you can contact him via email at elmoutaouakil.kh@gmail.com.

Nouredine Falih in 2013, he obtained a Doctor of Computer Science degree from the Faculty of Sciences and Technologies of Mohammedia, Morocco. Since 2014, he has been working as an associate professor at the Polydisciplinary Faculty of Sultan Moulay Slimane University in Beni Mellal, Morocco. With 18 years of professional experience in several renowned companies, his research interests revolve around information system governance, business intelligence, big data analytics, and digital agriculture. For further communication, he can be reached via email at nourfald@yahoo.fr.